

Coronavirus Disease Research Community – COVID-19

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Title: **Forecast of COVID19 infections, Brazil**

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I have analyzed the COVID19 infections in Brazil on May 7th, publishing the graphs on the following free blogs:

<https://covid19forecast.blogspot.com/>

<https://covid19southamerica.blogspot.com/>

The same figures are reported here.

The forecast of the total positive cases, according to the Verhulst equation is toward 180,000 cases, despite the observation that in the last few days the trend, in logarithmic scale, is linear, which means an exponential trend according to the Malthus equation.

The data of the new cases and deaths are still dispersed and a forecast has not been possible yet.